

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

DELIVERABLE 1.1

EGDI-Compatible Database of Mineral Deposits and Occurrences in Selected Regions in Finland, Poland, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Spain, and Zambia: Coordinates and Data Catalogue

This project has received funding under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101058178.

Project no. 101058178
Project acronym: AGEMERA
Project title: Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials
Call: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01
Start date of project: 01.08.2022
Duration: 36 months
Deliverable title: D1.1 EGDI-Compatible Database of Mineral Deposits and Occurrences in Selected Regions in Finland, Poland, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Spain, and Zambia: Coordinates and Data Catalogue
Due date of deliverable: 31.01.2024
Actual date of submission: 29.02.2024
Deliverable Lead Partner: University of Oulu
Dissemination level: Public

Author list

Name	Organisation
Marko Holma	University of Oulu, Kerttu Saalasti Institute
Marton Magyar	University of Oulu, Kerttu Saalasti Institute

Document History

Version	Date	Note	Revised by
01	16.01.2024	v0.1 Preliminary structure	Marko Holma
02	28.01.2024	v0.2 Draft	Marko Holma
03	17.02.2024	v0.5 New texts added	Marko Holma
04	22.02.2024	v0.6 Maps and new text added	Marton Magyar
05	26.02.2024	v0.7 Language checks	Marko Holma
06	29.02.2024	v1.0 Final edits after comments from the Reviewer	Marko Holma

Disclaimer

The content of the publication herein is the sole responsibility of the publishers and it does not necessarily represent the views expressed by the European Commission or its services.

While AGEMERA is funded by the European Union, views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA) can be held responsible for them.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the AGEMERA consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the AGEMERA Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the AGEMERA Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright notice

© AGEMERA Consortium, 2022-2025. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Executive Summary

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the nature of Deliverable 1.1 (D1.1) of the AGEMERA project's WPI. The D1.1 is a deposit and occurrence database that follows the European Geological Data Infrastructure (EGDI). The report outlines the project's background, objectives, methodology, data collection efforts, and preliminary insights derived from the data analysis, culminating in a discussion on the future implications for research and exploration in the target regions in the following countries: Finland, Poland, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Spain, and Zambia. The primary objective of D1.1 is to present the development and structure of the D1.1 database and to showcase the utility of the collected data when plotted on GIS (Geographic Information System) maps. A significant portion of the report is dedicated to explaining the EGDI format adopted for data documentation and integration. This methodology ensures that the data is not only standardised but also accessible to a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, exploration professionals, and policymakers.

Highlighted Info Box: Web Map Service (WMS)

Purpose: The WMS we have created serves as a powerful tool for accessing critical data related to mineral deposits and occurrences collected in this project.

Accessibility: Registered users gain exclusive access to browse, filter, and retrieve information for each visible deposit point.

Hosted Location: The service operates on the servers of the University of Oulu, Finland.

Registration Process: Interested users can register by contacting the designated administrator.

By integrating this WMS into our report, we enhance transparency, empower stakeholders, and advance informed decision-making.

Note: To delve deeper into the details of the Web Map Service, turn to page 30 of the report.

Contents

Disclaimer.....	2
Executive Summary.....	3
Contents	4
List of Acronyms.....	5
List of Figures.....	6
List of Tables.....	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1 Background.....	8
1.1.1 AGEMERA Project	8
1.1.2 Present Report's Place in the AGEMERA Project	9
1.1.3 Study Areas	10
1.2 Objectives of the Report.....	11
2. Methodology: the EGDI Format	13
3. Geological and Mineralisation Data from Target Regions in EGDI Format	15
3.1 Overview.....	15
3.2 Data Collection in AGEMERA	15
3.3 Metadata Documentation	22
3.3.1 Metadata Documentation in the EGDI Platform.....	22
3.3.2 Metadata Documentation During the D1.1 Data Collection	24
3.4 Overview of Partners Responsible for Data Collection	24
4. Preliminary Insights: Statistics and Data on GIS Maps	26
4.1 Geographical Distribution of Mineral Deposits and Occurrences in the D1.1 Database.....	26
4.2 Visualisation of Gathered Data in Each Deposit Zone.....	27
4.3 Web Map Service for Visualisation and Quality Control	30
5. The D1.1 Database: Bridging Disciplines, Connecting Continents	31
5.1 Interdisciplinary Application of the D1.1 Database	31
5.2 Facilitation of Future Research and Exploration	31
5.3 Contribution to the Geological Service for Europe and Zambia.....	32
6. Conclusions.....	33
Appendix 1.....	34
Selected Examples from the Excel Database.....	34
Appendix 2.....	35
Screenshots From a Selection of Deposits and Occurrences in the Excel Database.....	35

List of Acronyms

AGEMERA	Agile Exploration and Geo-modelling for European Critical Raw materials
CRM	Critical Raw Material
D	Deliverable
EGDI	European Geological Data Infrastructure
EGS	EuroGeoSurveys
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
GIS	Geographic Information System
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
SRID	Spatial Reference Identifier
WMS	Web Map Service
WP	Work Package

List of Figures

Figure 1. Project's main target regions and selected key trial sites.....	11
Figure 2. Example of data points in a selected area in Bulgaria.....	16
Figure 3. EGDI Metadata view.....	23
Figure 4. The collected deposit data from Finland.....	27
Figure 5. The collected deposit data from Poland.....	27
Figure 6. The collected deposit data from Croatia and Bosnia-Herzegovina.....	28
Figure 7. The collected deposit data from Bulgaria.....	28
Figure 8. The collected deposit data from Spain.....	29
Figure 9. The collected deposit data from Zambia.....	29
Figure 10. The AGAMERA WebMap service running in a browser window.....	30

List of Tables

Table 1. Summary of dropdown list contents of the columns “Occurrence Type” and “Deposit Group”, as defined in the EGDI spreadsheet version used for data collection..	16
Table 2. Summary of dropdown list contents of the columns “Deposit Type” and “Inspire Commodity”, as defined in the EGDI spreadsheet version used for data collection.....	17
Table 3. Summary of dropdown list contents of the columns “CRM 2023“, “Inspire Commodity“, “Commodity Importance“, and “Mine Status“, as defined in the EGDI spreadsheet version used for data collection.....	20
Table 4. Overview of partners responsible for data collection activities in Task 1.1 leading to D1.1.....	25
Table 5. Summary of mineral deposits and occurrences by country.....	26

1. Introduction

The name of this deliverable has been changed from the original “A database with metadata documentation of geological properties and mineralisation footprints of target regions in EGDI compatible formats” to better fit to its true contents. The revised name for the deliverable is now “EGDI-Compatible Database of Mineral Deposits and Occurrences in Selected Regions in Finland, Poland, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Spain, and Zambia: Coordinates and Data Catalogue”. This new name more accurately reflects the content and purpose of D1.1. It is essential to have a precise name to facilitate discoverability through database and internet searches, thereby promoting open access principles and ensuring long-term data availability for the benefit of society.

1.1 Background

1.1.1 AGEMERA Project

The AGEMERA project focuses on advancing mineral exploration methods in the European Union (EU) and Zambia to meet the demands of a low-carbon and digital economy. Utilising a combination of conventional and state-of-the-art geological and geophysical surveys, the project aims to map Critical Raw Material (CRM) resources across approximately 4,700 km² in seven countries. It will employ three innovative, non-invasive survey techniques — passive seismic methods, multi-sensing drone system, and muon-based multidetector density detection system (utilising a novel astroparticle physics technique called muon imaging or muography) — to enhance the accuracy of existing genetic mineral system models. Concurrently, the project will engage with stakeholders to introduce United Nations Framework Classification (UNFC) guidelines for mineral resources and will undertake extensive public outreach, targeting an audience of 5,000,000 citizens by 2030. Additionally, AGEMERA will develop an open-access SoftGIS database (GIS stands for “Geographic Information System”) to capture social, cultural, environmental, and economic concerns related to mining, thereby facilitating the creation of socio-economic potential maps to be used alongside geological potential maps. This report focuses on describing the results of activities relating to Deliverable 1.1 (D1.1) of the Geological Work Package (WP) of the AGEMERA project, i.e., WP1.

AGEMERA is leading the charge in transforming how Europe and Zambia explore for Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) that are needed for the low-carbon and digital revolution.

Spanning seven countries and covering a vast 4,700 km², the project leverages both traditional and cutting-edge exploration methods, including:

- **State-of-the-art surveys:** Employing geological and geophysical techniques to map CRM resources.
- **Innovative tools:** Unleashing three non-invasive methods:
 - **Passive seismic methods**
 - **Multi-sensing drone system**
 - **Muon imaging (cosmic-ray muography)**
- **Enhanced accuracy:** Refining existing mineral system models for pinpointing CRMs with greater precision.

Nevertheless, AGEMERA goes beyond just finding resources. It engages stakeholders, embracing the United Nations Framework Classification (UNFC) guidelines for responsible mineral resource management. It also prioritises public outreach, aiming to reach 5 million people by 2030 through engaging initiatives. Furthermore, the project recognises the social, cultural, environmental, and economic aspects of mining. It builds an open-access SoftGIS database to capture these concerns, paving the way for "socio-economic potential maps" alongside geological ones.

1.1.2 Present Report's Place in the AGEMERA Project

This report constitutes a deliverable D1.1 within WP1 of the AGEMERA project. AGEMERA encompasses seven distinct WPs. These are structured as follows:

- **WP1: European CRM Potential:** Assessing the potential for CRMs within Europe.
- **WP2: Impact of CRM on Green & Digital Transition:** Analysing the influence of CRMs on the advancement towards a greener and more digital society.
- **WP3: Geophysical Data Acquisition:** Gathering geophysical data essential for CRM exploration in the selected target areas.
- **WP4: Data Processing, Fusion & Sharing:** Processing, consolidating, and sharing acquired data.
- **WP5: Dissemination, Communication & Collaboration:** Ensuring effective communication and collaboration throughout the project with both the project partners and external stakeholders.
- **WP6: Exploitation:** Leveraging project outcomes for practical applications.
- **WP7: Management:** Overseeing the smooth execution and progress of the project.

WP1 is further subdivided into the following tasks:

- **Task 1.1: Crustal Structure, Mineral System Model, and Mineralisation Footprints**

This task involves a comprehensive review of literature and databases to understand the geological, geochemical, and geophysical characteristics of CRM deposits in Europe and Zambia. It aims to deepen the understanding of crustal structures, mineral systems, and mineralisation footprints. It focuses on transcrustal geological domain boundaries and their role in mineralisation.

Note: The current report is a deliverable of this task.

- **Task 1.2: Field Research and Sampling**

Field research and sampling in selected CRM deposits across Europe and Zambia to collect new data. This includes mapping, sampling, and logging in key regions, supporting computer-based modelling efforts. The task emphasises the collection of conventional and novel field data to aid in the understanding of CRMs in the selected study areas (see Section 1.1.3 for details).

- **Task 1.3: Novel Mineral System Data for CRMs in Target Sites**

This task combines new field data with laboratory analyses to provide insights into the grade and distribution of CRMs at target sites. It involves advanced analytical techniques to generate novel geochemical and mineral-chemistry data, supporting computer modelling and improving mineral system models.

- **Task 1.4: Computer-Based Modelling**

This task focuses on modelling CRM districts using historical and new data from field surveys and analyses. The goal is to create a holistic view of CRM deposition and identify new exploration areas using structural modelling software and analysis tools.

- **Task 1.5: Development of New and Improved Mineral System Models for CRM Ore Deposit Types**

Utilises outputs from the preceding tasks to refine or develop new mineral system models for CRM-hosting ore deposits. This task aims to systematically document geological, mineralogical, geochemical, and geochronological characteristics to differentiate essential features of CRM deposits and guide future exploration and development efforts.

1.1.3 Study Areas

The AGEMERA project concentrates its research and technology tests in several geological areas in Europe and one in Zambia. Both the areas of interest and the pilot sites where muography is piloted are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Project's main target regions (polygons) and selected key trial sites (asterisks).

1.2 Objectives of the Report

The primary objective of this report is to present an account of the development and structure of the D1.1 database, including a visual representation of the collected data when plotted on maps as a series of images. Constructed in accordance with European Geological Data Infrastructure (EGDI) standards, the database aims to ensure widespread accessibility and interoperability. In the AGEMERA proposal, D1.1 is categorised as "data"; thus, strictly speaking, this report is not a mandatory accompaniment to the provided data. However, it aims to serve as a form of metadata

relating to the D1.1 database. The specific objectives of the report are outlined as follows:

- **Present the database structure at the moment of data collection:** We delineate the structure of the D1.1 database.
- **Interdisciplinary application:** To illustrate the interdisciplinary application of the D1.1 database across geoscience research, mineral exploration, and environmental assessment. The report aims to showcase the potential of the database to support a broad spectrum of scientific inquiries and industrial activities related to CRMs.
- **Facilitation of future research and exploration:** To outline how the D1.1 database serves as a foundational resource for guiding future research initiatives and exploration strategies. This includes identifying potential areas for new CRM discoveries and contributing to the sustainable management and exploitation of Europe and Zambia's mineral resources.
- **Contribution to geological service for Europe:** To underscore the contribution of the D1.1 database to the overarching goals of the European Geological Data Infrastructure (EGDI) and its role in advancing the vision of establishing a comprehensive Geological Service for Europe. This report aims to reflect on how integrating the D1.1 database within EGDI enhances the accessibility and utility of geological data at a pan-European level.

2. Methodology: the EGDI Format

“EGDI” stands for “The European Geological Data Infrastructure”. EGDI is an ambitious central element that combines European geological data into a single, accessible platform. It is designed and maintained by the Geological Surveys of Europe, which are also known as EuroGeoSurveys (EGS). EGDI’s mission aligns with the broader objective of establishing a comprehensive geological service for Europe, serving as a central repository for pan-European and national geological datasets and services offered by Geological Survey Organisations across the continent.

[Map Viewer](#) is one of the tools available for accessing the information in EGDI. This service is a powerful and easy-to-use online application for visualising and querying spatial information through interactive maps. It also includes various tools to perform further data analysis. For example, the user can select different base layers and add layers from all the geoscientific topics covered by EGDI. Data in the layers can also be accessed through OGC view and download services. Many data can also be downloaded as GIS (Geographic Information System) files. Herein, "OGC" refers to the Open Geospatial Consortium, which is an international organisation committed to making geospatial information and services FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The OGC establishes standards to enhance the quality, accessibility, and interoperability of geospatial information. This enables platforms like the EGDI Map Viewer to display and share geospatial data effectively. In summary, while AGEMERA-related deposit data supports the EGDI platform, the latter adheres to OGC standards.

The EGDI data search tool allows users to discover and access available datasets, view their metadata and select, display and download subsets of elements from multiple datasets. The Map Services and Layers list of all the map layers is accessible on the EGDI Map Viewer. It shows whether the layer has metadata and what the current status (if it is working) of the corresponding web service is.

In recent years, the operation and maintenance of the EGDI have been financed by EuroGeoSurveys, with GEUS, CGS, GeoZS, IGME, BRGM, and BGS—members of EuroGeoSurveys—undertaking the operations, maintenance, and enhancements. These activities are conducted in tight collaboration with the Spatial Information Expert Group of EuroGeoSurveys.

Based on the description of [the EGDI webpage background description](#), EGDI served originally as the foundational framework for the Information Platform created through the GeoERA programme's GIP project, which was active from July 2018 to October 2021. This project significantly expanded EGDI's capabilities. However, in September 2022, a new Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action titled "Geological Service for Europe (GSEU)" was launched for a duration of five years. This project aims to advance the development of EGDI further.

EGDI enables access to raw material data via the European Commission's Joint Research Center's Raw Materials Information System (RMIS). Additionally, EGDI is set to

act as the conduit between Geological Survey Organisations, their geological data, and digital services, and the European Plate Observing System (EPOS), facilitating integration upon the latter's activation.

3. Geological and Mineralisation Data from Target Regions in EGDl Format

3.1 Overview

The partners working on Task 1.1 (Table 4) have collected geological and mineralisation-related data to develop an Excel database that captures the geological properties and mineralisation footprints of targeted CRM districts in Finland, Poland, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Spain, and Zambia. This database, designated as D1.1 when combined with the present report, is structured to adhere to the European Geological Data Infrastructure (EGDI) standards, ensuring compatibility and accessibility for stakeholders. The purpose of this section is to detail the creation, structure, and content of the D1.1 data.

3.2 Data Collection in AGEMERA

In Task 1.1, the teams participating in the task collected tabulated Excel data from their respective areas of responsibility by following the EGDl spreadsheet format. The data collected are 2D geospatial data used for visualising CMR-hosting or CRM-indicative mineral deposits and occurrences in the EGDl online map layers.

The development of the D1.1 database—a series of Excel sheets from all the studied areas in Finland, Poland, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Spain, and Zambia—involved systematic literature and database reviews carried out by the responsible teams in these countries. Each team focused on the current state of knowledge regarding the local mineral deposits and occurrences that are not yet included in [the EGDl map platform](#).

The compiled data is organised into 21 columns within the Excel spreadsheet. For details, see Appendix 1.

Each team was instructed to populate the spreadsheets with data on mineral deposits and occurrences to the best of their abilities. Coordinates were converted to the EPSG:4326 standard, ensuring a minimum accuracy of five decimal places. The Excel spreadsheet featured a mix of empty cells for free text entry, and, in certain sections, pre-defined drop-down lists established by the EGDl. Tables 1, 2 and 3 summarise the dropdown list contents of the key columns as specified in the version of the EGDl Spreadsheets available at the time of data collection. Note that the texts in the three provided tables below include all the typos present in the original spreadsheet to ensure better data reproducibility.

Figure 2 shows an example of data points located in a selected area in Bulgaria.

Figure 2. Example of data points in a selected area in Bulgaria.

Table 1. Summary of dropdown list contents of the columns “Occurrence Type” and “Deposit Group”, as defined in the EGDI spreadsheet version used for data collection.

Occurrence Type	Deposit Group
occurrence	residual/surficial
prospect	other
mineral deposit	sediment-hosted
field	ultramafic / mafic
district	felsic-intermediate igneous rock related
project	metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein
mineralized zone	marine volcanic association
7 options in total	alkaline igneous rocks, other
	marine volcanic association, other
	metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein, other
	placer, other

epithermal, other
ultramafic / mafic, other
alkaline igneous rocks
sedimentary
epithermal, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein
sediment-hosted, ultramafic / mafic
residual/surficial, other
bulk rock material
contact metamorphism
marine volcanic association, felsic-intermediate igneous rock related
sediment-hosted, felsic-intermediate igneous rock related
sediment-hosted, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein
placer
epithermal
contact metamorphism, other
26 options in total

Table 2. Summary of dropdown list contents of the columns “Deposit Type” and “Inspire Commodity”, as defined in the EGDI spreadsheet version used for data collection.

Deposit Type	Inspire Commodity
high-sulphidation	Vanadium (metal)
banded iron formation (BIF)	Vanadium pentoxide
layered complex	Tungsten (metal)
ophiolite	Titanium, general (TiO ₂)
mafic to ultramafic intrusion	Tantalum (metal)
sedimentary	Strontium
non-organic (incl. U)	Scandium (metal)
iron oxide copper gold (IOCG)	Phosphorous
orogenic gold	Phosphorous pentoxide (P ₂ O ₅)
porphyry	Phosphate rock
skarn and carbonate replacement	Platinum group metals (refined metal)

iron oxide apatite (IOA)	Palladium (metal)
skarn and carbonate replacement, mafic to ultramafic intrusion	Platinum (metal)
sandstone-hosted	Rhodium (metal)
skarn and carbonate replacement, granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, pegmatite aplite	Iridium (metal)
granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, mafic to ultramafic intrusion, pegmatite aplite	Ruthenium (metal)
vein, including polymetallic and 5 element vein (Bi, Co, Ni, Ag, U)	Niobium (metal)
granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites	Nickel (metal)
mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits	Graphite
skarn and carbonate replacement, vein, including polymetallic and 5 element vein (Bi, Co, Ni, Ag, U)	Graphite (flake)
skarn and carbonate replacement, granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites	Graphite (amorphous)
sediment hosted copper	Manganese (metal)
low-sulphidation	Manganese ore (gross weight)
unsaturated and saturated syenitic and alkali granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites	Magnesium (metal)
organic	Light rare earth element
shale-hosted (incl. SEDEX)	Cerium (Ce ₂ O ₃)
carbonate-hosted	Lanthanum
shoreline / marine placer	Neodymium
magmatic hydrothermal	Praseodymium
bimodal and felsic volcanism Cu-Pb-Zn VMS and transitional magmatic deposits	Lithium (metal)
paleoplacer	Lithium oxide (Li ₂ O)
granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, pegmatite aplite	Heavy rare earth element
pegmatite aplite	Yttrium
metamorphic	Yttrium Oxide (Y ₂ O ₃)
evaporite	Hafnium (metal)
carbonatite	Germanium
phosphorite	Gallium (metal)
anorthosite	Fluorite or fluospar (CaF ₂)

laterite	Fluorine
komatiite	Feldspar, nepheline
rare metal granite	Copper (metal)
mafic to ultramafic effusive volcanism	Black coal
sediment hosted copper, volcanogenic massive Ssulphide (VMS)	Cobalt (metal)
mafic to ultramafic intrusion, sediment hosted copper	Boron
dimension stone, Industrial Rock	Bismuth (metal)
mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits, anorthosite	Beryllium (metal)
bauxite	Baryte or Barite (BaSO4)
volcanogenic massive Ssulphide (VMS)	Arsenic (Metal)
gossan	Antimony (metal)
mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits, vein, including polymetallic and 5 element vein (Bi, Co, Ni, Ag, U)	Aluminium, primary
sedimentary manganese	Bauxite
iron oxide apatite (IOA), skarn and carbonate replacement	Alumina
kimberlite and lamproite	Titanium, ilmenite
granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, vein, including polymetallic and 5 element vein (Bi, Co, Ni, Ag, U)	Tantalum pentoxide (Ta2O5)
aggregate, Industrial Rock	Samarium (metal)
Carlin-type carbonate-hosted Au-Ag	Terbium
sandstone-hosted, sediment hosted copper	Europium
sandstone-hosted, volcanogenic massive Ssulphide (VMS)	Ytterbium
granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, sediment hosted copper	Lutetium
granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, pegmatite aplite, sediment hosted copper	Borates (B2O3)
skarn and carbonate replacement, mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits	Beryllium (BeO)
skarn and carbonate replacement, sediment hosted copper, volcanogenic massive Ssulphide (VMS)	61 options in total
mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits, volcanogenic massive Ssulphide (VMS)	
oolitic iron / ironstone	

mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits, mafic to ultramafic intrusion
vein, including polymetallic and 5 element vein (Bi, Co, Ni, Ag, U), volcanogenic massive Ssulphide (VMS)
skarn and carbonate replacement, volcanogenic massive Ssulphide (VMS)
vein, including polymetallic and 5 element vein (Bi, Co, Ni, Ag, U), sediment hosted copper
alluvial placer
ophiolite, non-organic (incl. U)
ophiolite, phosphorite
laterite, non-organic (incl. U)
dimension stone
sedimentary manganese, organic
sedimentary manganese, carbonate-hosted
greisen
mafic to ultramafic effusive volcanism, non-organic (incl. U)
mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits, non-organic (incl. U)
stratiform barite
bauxite, dimension stone
phosphorite, evaporite
phosphorite, shoreline / marine placer
polymetallic manto
carbonate-hosted, sandstone-hosted
sandstone-hosted, carbonate-hosted
mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits, ophiolite
vein, including polymetallic and 5 element vein (Bi, Co, Ni, Ag, U), non-organic (incl. U)
bauxite, sandstone-hosted
mafic volcanism Cu–Zn massive sulphide deposits, sedimentary manganese
eluvial placer
90 options in total

Table 3. Summary of dropdown list contents of the columns “CRM 2023”, “Inspire Commodity”, “Commodity Importance”, and “Mine Status”, as defined in the EGDI spreadsheet version used for data collection.

CRM 2023	Element	Commodity Importance	Mine Status
vanadium	V	Not specified	historic
tungsten	W	occurrence	no mine

titanium metal	Ti	small deposit	operating
tantalum	Ta	medium sized deposit	closed
strontium	Sr	large deposit	notOperating
scandium	Sc	very large deposit	abandoned
phosphorous	P	6 options in total	retention
phosphate rock	phosphate rock		pendingApproval
PGM	PGM		feasibility
niobium	Nb		operatingContinuously
nickel	Ni		underDevelopment
natural graphite	natural graphite		closed,operating
manganese	Mn		construction
magnesium	Mg		operatingIntermittently
LREE	LREE		closed,historic
lithium	Li		careAndMaintenance
HREE	HREE		16 options in total
hafnium	Hf		
germanium	Ge		
gallium	Ga		
fluorspar	F		
feldspar	feldspar		
copper	Cu		
coking coal	coking coal		
cobalt	Co		
borate	B		
bismuth	Bi		
beryllium	Be		
baryte	Ba		
arsenic	As		
antimony	Sb		
aluminium or bauxite	Al		
32 options in total	32 options in total		

3.3 Metadata Documentation

3.3.1 Metadata Documentation in the EGDl Platform

The EGDl platform employs two distinct methods for managing metadata. Firstly, [the EGDl Metadata Catalogue](#) serves as the primary gateway for accessing metadata that describes data resources and other relevant information in a standardised format. This catalogue comprehensively details only digital and structured information, such as geographic and spatial datasets, dataset series, and spatial data services—including Web Map Services (WMS), Web Feature Services (WFS), multidimensional models, and other digital offerings like web applications. On the other hand, metadata for unstructured documents are systematically catalogued and updated within the EGDl Document Repository.

While access to metadata through the EGDl Metadata Catalogue is open to all for viewing and searching, the capabilities for insertion and modification are restricted to authorised users. This dual approach ensures both broad accessibility for public users and controlled data management for contributors.

Figure 3 shows a view of the EGDl Metadata Catalogue front page.

Search text

Everywhere
 Title
 Title + Abstract

Resource type

INSPIRE theme

GeoERA keywords

Project name

Data contact (custodian)

Country (custodian)

Spatial scope

Metadata language

Harvested from

Sort by

✕ Clear

Metadata 4698

1:250K Geological Maps of Northern Ireland version 2

The 1:250k Geological Maps of Northern Ireland comprise the Superficial Deposits Map (Drift, 1991) and the Bedrock Map (Solid Geology, 1997). These maps identify landscape areas based on their lithology. The scale of the maps is 1:250 000 and provides a simplified interpretation of the geology that may be used as a guide at a regional level, but should not be relied on for local geology. Superficial deposits are younger geological deposits formed during the most recent geological time; the Quaternary. These...

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey, United Kingdom, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

10k sheet data files

An important paper archive of a wide variety of miscellaneous geological information organised on the basis of its location within 1:10 000 scale geological map sheet areas in Great Britain. The majority of the data has been produced or collected from a wide variety of sources by BGS staff since 1835. Mainly acquired as part of the mapping programme new information is added on a regular basis. The data may not fit into any of the main collections, but is valuable for future projects and answering enquiries

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey, United Kingdom, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

16S rRNA Gene Sequencing of Filtered Groundwater from 8 Boreholes in Cambodia (NERC grant NE/P01304X/1)

This dataset represents the raw reads from sequencing the V4 hyper-variable region of the 16S rRNA gene on an Illumina MiSeq platform. The samples are filtered groundwater samples from 8 boreholes from a sandy-dominated site and a clay-dominated site in Cambodia that show arsenic concentrations above the WHO recommended limit, and were collected in May 2019.

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey, United Kingdom, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

1997, ConocoPhillips, UKCS 164/7-A, Site Survey, BGS Reference Number CS97SS0001

An oil and gas industry rig site survey acquired between April and May 1997. The block number traversed was 164/7.

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey (BGS), UK, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

1997, Hess, Block 5604/29 and 5604/30 South Arne, Site Survey, BGS Reference Number AH97SS0001

An oil and gas industry geophysical site survey acquired in December 1997. The block numbers traversed were 5604/29, 5604/30 South Arne.

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey (BGS), UK, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

1997, Hess, Flora Field Development Block 31/26c, Site Survey, BGS Reference Number AH97SS0002

An oil and gas industry site survey acquired in December 1997. The block numbers traversed were 31/26 and 31/27.

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey (BGS), UK, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

1997, Kerr McGee North Sea (UK) Ltd, Janice Field Development (UKCS 30/17 to UKCS 30/13), Pipeline/Cable Route Survey, BGS Reference Number KM97SS0002

An oil and gas industry site survey for a pipeline/cable route (Janice UKCS 30/17 oil export to wye-piece tie-in UKCS 30/13) acquired between October and November 1997. The block numbers traversed were 30/12, 30/13, 30/16, 30/17 and 30/18.

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey (BGS), UK, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

1997, Kerr McGee North Sea (UK) Ltd, Janice Field Development (UKCS 30/17 to UKCS 30/7), Pipeline/Cable Route Survey, BGS Reference Number KM97SS0001

An oil and gas industry site survey for a pipeline/cable route (gas export Janice UKCS 30/17 to Judy UKCS 30/7) acquired between October and November 1997. The block numbers traversed were 30/12, 30/17 and 30/7.

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey (BGS), UK, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

1998, Hess, Bittern And Flora Developments, Site Survey, BGS Reference Number AH98SS0006

An oil and gas industry geophysical and geotechnical site survey acquired between December and February 1998. The block number traversed was 31/26.

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey (BGS), UK, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

1998, Hess, Bittern And West Guillemot Development, Site Survey, BGS Reference Number AH98SS0002

An oil and gas industry geophysical and geotechnical site survey acquired between December and February 1998. The block numbers traversed were 21/24, 21/25, 21/29, 21/30, 22/21, 22/26, 28/4, 28/5 and 29/1.

Metadata Contact: British Geological Survey (BGS), UK, Date Stamp: 2024-02-12

1 / 470 >>>

Figure 3. EGDI Metadata view.
(<https://egdi.geology.cz/>)

3.3.2 Metadata Documentation During the D1.1 Data Collection

Within the AGEMERA proposal, D1.1 is classified as 'data' to be provided to EGD administrators (data has been submitted to them on 29.02.2024). Therefore, strictly speaking, this report is not a mandatory supplement to the provided data. Nevertheless, given the complex nature of the data collection process, the responsible partner for D1.1, namely Partner UO, has chosen to enhance the original outcome by compiling this report. This document serves as a valuable source of information both internally, during the remainder of the AGEMERA project (for instance, there are plans to update the database should new information emerge or be produced), and externally, regarding future data usage (as will be discussed in Section 5) and data reproducibility. In summary, this report is intended to act as a form of metadata associated with the D1.1 database.

3.4 Overview of Partners Responsible for Data Collection

The AGEMERA Partners that collected the data from each of the target countries' selected areas are shown in Table 4. Where necessary, the responsible partners received support from AGEMERA industrial partners, i.e., the local mining companies. These supporting partners have also been added to Table 4.

Table 4. Overview of partners responsible for data collection activities in Task 1.1 leading to D1.1. Asterisks in the partner short names denote partners that provided support to the primary partner, which is highlighted in bold.

Metadata Regarding the Teams Collecting Data					
Country: Partner	Short name	Partner Name	PIC	Partner Type	Country: Data Origin
Finland	LAT	Latitude 66 Cobalt	889796036	Industrial	Finland
	CUP	KGHM Cuprum Research & Development Centre	999495470	Research	
Poland	KGHM*	KGHM Polska Miedź	999495470	Industrial	Poland
	UZG	University of Zagreb	998157258	Academic	
Croatia	UZG	University of Zagreb	998157258	Academic	Croatia
Bosnia-Herzegovina	RBJ*	Bauxite Mines Jajce	889720473	Industrial	Bosnia-Herzegovina
	RBP*	Bauxite Mines Posušje	889720861	Industrial	
Bulgaria	BAS	Geological Institute of Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	996371779	Academic	Bulgaria
	ASSAR*	Assarel Medet AD	950669162	Industrial	
Spain	CSIC	Agencia estatal consejo superior de investigaciones científicas	999991722	Research	Spain
	MATSA*	Minas de Aguas Tenidas SA	932277380	Industrial	
Zambia	UNZA	University of Zambia, IWRM Centre	999887932	Academic	Zambia

4. Preliminary Insights: Statistics and Data on GIS Maps

4.1 Geographical Distribution of Mineral Deposits and Occurrences in the D1.1 Database

Statistics regarding how many data points were collected from each of the target countries for the D1.1 database are summarised in Table 5. This compilation offers a clear overview of the geographical distribution of mineral deposits and occurrences, reflecting the extensive data-gathering efforts undertaken by the research teams.

Table 5. Summary of mineral deposits and occurrences by country, highlighting the number of identified sites in Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, Poland, Spain, and Zambia, respectively. The databased contains a total of 2041 entries.

Counts of Mineral Deposits and Occurrences Across Selected Countries	
Country	Deposits and Occurrences (Count)
Bosnia-Herzegovina	126
Bulgaria	66
Croatia	106
Finland	14
Poland	102
Spain	355
Zambia	1272
Total Count	2041

4.2 Visualisation of Gathered Data in Each Deposit Zone

The following figures (Figs. 4-9) illustrate how the collected data plots on the GIS maps. These images were produced before the data was submitted to the EGDI contact point (<https://egdi.geology.cz/about>).

Figure 4. The collected deposit data from Finland. Points present the deposit locations.

Figure 5. The collected deposit data from Poland. Points present the deposit locations.

Figure 6. The collected deposit data from Croatia and Bosnia-Herzegovina. Points present the deposit locations.

Figure 7. The collected deposit data from Bulgaria. Points present the deposit locations.

Figure 8. The collected deposit data from Spain. Points present the deposit locations.

Figure 9. The collected deposit data from Zambia. Points present the deposit locations.

4.3 Web Map Service for Visualisation and Quality Control

Utilising the spatial data gathered from partners, a joint database has been created and hosted on a password-protected Web Map Service (WMS). The WMS allows registered users to browse, filter, and access data for each visible deposit point. The service runs on the servers of the University of Oulu. Registration is possible by reaching out to the administrator.

Figure 10. The AGAMERA WebMap service running in a browser window.

Link to the service:

<https://www oulu.fi/my/agemera/site/>

*Administrator: Marton Magyar,
marton.magyar@oulu.fi.*

5. The D1.1 Database: Bridging Disciplines, Connecting Continents

5.1 Interdisciplinary Application of the D1.1 Database

The mineral deposit and occurrence data collected for the D1.1 database fills the gaps in the current EGD map with significant new contributions from the selected countries. We envisage that the data we have collected will facilitate numerous interdisciplinary applications, highlighting its potential to enhance scientific inquiries and industrial activities related to CRMs. These include, but are not limited to:

- **Geoscience research:** The database provides an extensive repository of mineral deposit and occurrence data that can significantly enhance the understanding of CRM deposits' formation processes, distribution, and characteristics. Researchers can utilise this data to develop new geological models, refine existing theories, and conduct comparative studies across different regions.
- **Mineral exploration:** For the mineral exploration sector, the D1.1 database offers invaluable insights into the location, grade, and extent of CRM deposit zones. By using the EGD database updated with the data we have collected, exploration companies can optimise their search strategies, reduce exploration risks, and efficiently allocate resources towards the most promising prospects.
- **Environmental assessment:** The data within the D1.1 database aids in assessing the environmental impacts of mining activities, facilitating the development of strategies to mitigate harmful effects on ecosystems and communities. Environmental scientists can utilise this data to conduct risk assessments, evaluate conservation priorities, and recommend sustainable mining practices.

5.2 Facilitation of Future Research and Exploration

The D1.1 data serves as a cornerstone for future research initiatives and exploration strategies in the quest for new CRM discoveries in the selected European countries and Zambia. We envisage that our data bears significant potential in encouraging innovative approaches to mineral exploration and research, as well as contributing significantly to the sustainable management and exploitation of mineral resources. It may, for example, facilitate the following future research and exploration activities:

- **Guiding research initiatives:** By providing a rich source of data on CRM deposits, the database enables researchers to identify knowledge gaps, formulate new hypotheses, and pursue groundbreaking studies in mineralogy, geochemistry, and environmental sciences.
- **Enhancing exploration strategies:** The data are useful for exploration professionals as they provide the tools to pinpoint underexplored areas with high potential for CRM deposits. This targeted approach not only increases the efficiency of exploration efforts but also supports the discovery of new mineral resources critical to the European and Zambian economies.

5.3 Contribution to the Geological Service for Europe and Zambia

The integration of the D1.1 data within the EGDI represents a significant advancement towards the realisation of a comprehensive Geological Service for Europe. The new data contributes to EGDI's overarching goals, enhancing the accessibility, utility, and interoperability of geological data across the continent. These aspects can be summarised:

- **Enhancing data accessibility:** By complying with the EGDI standards, the D1.1 database, upon integration into the EGDI platform, ensures that geological data on recognised CRM deposits previously unavailable in the EGDI platform become readily accessible to a diverse audience, including researchers, exploration professionals, policymakers, and the general public.
- **Supporting data interoperability:** The database's adherence to EGDI-compatible formats facilitates a unified approach to geological research and mineral exploration.
- **Advancing the geological service vision:** The D1.1 database's contribution to EGDI is a demonstration of the power of collaborative efforts aimed at establishing a Geological Service for Europe. By pooling resources, standardising data formats, and promoting open access to information, the database plays a crucial role in advancing geoscientific knowledge and supporting sustainable development initiatives across the continent.

6. Conclusions

The D1.1 database not only serves the immediate needs of the geoscientific community but also lays the groundwork for future advancements in the exploration, research, and management of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) in Europe and Zambia, with potential applicability beyond these regions. As we reflect on the significance of this work, we recognise its potential impact on various stakeholders.

1. **Geoscientific community:** The D1.1 database provides a valuable resource for geoscientists, enabling them to access historical and new data related to mineral deposits and occurrences. By consolidating information, it facilitates informed decision-making and supports research endeavours.
2. **Educators and students:** These groups can explore the database to enhance their understanding of critical raw materials. By promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange, the D1.1 database has a potential to enhance scientific progress in various fields.
3. **Decision-makers:** Policymakers, regulators, and government bodies can leverage this database to formulate evidence-based policies. The availability of openly accessible data ensures transparency and aids in sustainable resource management.
4. **Mining professionals:** Industry experts benefit from the D1.1 database by gaining insights into mineral resources. This knowledge informs exploration strategies, extraction techniques, and resource utilisation, ultimately contributing to efficient and responsible mining practices.
5. **NGOs and other stakeholders:** Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and community representatives can encourage the adoption of responsible mining practices using the data provided. Accessible information empowers them to engage in meaningful discussions and advocate for sustainable resource utilisation.

Looking ahead, continuous updates and expansion of the EGD (European Geological Data Infrastructure) database and map services, will further enhance its value over time. By translating complex geological data into an easily accessible format, the provided D1.1 data will be part of a more informed and sustainable future.

Appendix 1

Selected Examples from the Excel Database

The Excel file that was used to collect deposit and occurrence data in the EGD data format was organised into the following 21 columns. The term “Inspire Commodity” is explained after the list. Appendix 2 shows a selection of data as it is in the Excel database, illustrating examples of various types of mineral deposits and occurrences across the studied regions.

- Name (= Locality)
- Country
- Occurrence Type
- Deposit Group
- Deposit Type
- Inspire Commodity (= INSPIRE Commodity) *
- CRM 2023
- Element
- Commodity Importance
- Mine Status
- Mining Activity Types
- Has Ore Measures
- Endowment
- Reserves
- Resources
- UNFC
- Total Production
- Longitude
- Latitude
- SRID
- CRM 2023 importance

* The above-mentioned “INSPIRE Commodity” data field refers to the INSPIRE registry, which is managed by the European Commission Joint Research Centre B6 Unit. The INSPIRE Registry provides a unique access point to several centrally managed registers used in the scope of the INSPIRE Directive. The platform supports data providers, solution providers, and INSPIRE national coordinators in searching for concepts and finding their corresponding reference codes. The INSPIRE registry content is managed through a transparent governance workflow, which includes how to handle change proposals. Mineral resources in the INSPIRE registry include, for example, metal ores and industrial minerals. However, energy resources such as coal, oil and gas are excluded in this theme, as they are found in the theme "energy resources".

Appendix 2

Screenshots From a Selection of Deposits and Occurrences in the Excel Database

(note: the image continues to the next page)

name	country	occurrence_type	deposit_group	deposit_type
Kongora	BiH	Mineral Deposit	Sedimentary	Bauxite
Funtana	Croatia	Mineral Deposit	Sedimentary	Bauxite
Kapustavuoma	Finland	occurrence	sediment-hosted	sedimentary
Kiimavuoma	Finland	occurrence	metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein, other	skarn and carbonate replacement
Petäjaskoski	Finland	occurrence	metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein, other	orogenic gold
Sotkavaara	Finland	occurrence	ultramafic / mafic	mafic to ultramafic intrusion
Vähäjoki	Finland	mineral deposit	metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein, other	iron oxide copper gold (IOCG)
Boguszów	Poland	mineral deposit	metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein	magmatic hydrothermal
Budryk	Poland	mineral deposit	sedimentary	organic
Bytom Odrzański	Poland	mineral deposit	sediment-hosted	sediment hosted copper
Góra Sosnia (Dziwiszów)	Poland	mineral deposit	other	granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, mafic to ultramafic intrusion, pegmatite aplite
Niedźwiada II	Poland	occurrence	epithermal	phosphorite
Adolfina	Spain	mineral deposit	sediment-hosted	sedimentary manganese
Aguas Blancas	Spain	mineral deposit	Other	shale-hosted (incl. SEDEX)
Almagrera	Spain	mineral deposit	marine volcanic association	volcanogenic massive Ssulphide (VMS)
Riotinto (Cerro Colorado)	Spain	mineral deposit	residual/surficial	gossan
1624_DK_2	Zambia	occurrence	epithermal, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein	iron oxide copper gold (IOCG)
1625_CK_1	Zambia	occurrence	epithermal, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein	iron oxide copper gold (IOCG)
1625_CK2	Zambia	occurrence	epithermal, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein	iron oxide copper gold (IOCG)
21_ML_PEG_GREAT_EAST_ROAD	Zambia	occurrence	epithermal, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein	gossan
ALONS	Zambia	occurrence	sediment-hosted	sediment hosted copper
AREA_52	Zambia	occurrence	sediment-hosted, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein	iron oxide copper gold (IOCG)
ITAPIRA	Zambia	occurrence	sediment-hosted, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein	sediment hosted copper
ITAPIRA_FE	Zambia	occurrence	sediment-hosted, metasomatic replacement or hydrothermal shear or vein	iron oxide copper gold (IOCG)
JIMMY	Zambia	occurrence	felsic-intermediate igneous rock related	granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites
Chelopech	Bulgaria	mineral deposit	epithermal	high-sulphidation
Orlovo Gnezdo	Bulgaria	mineral deposit	felsic-intermediate igneous rock related	porphyry
Chervena mogila	Bulgaria	occurrence	epithermal	high-sulphidation
Elshitsa	Bulgaria	mineral deposit	epithermal	high-sulphidation
Rossen	Bulgaria	mineral deposit	felsic-intermediate igneous rock related	iron oxide copper gold (IOCG)
Kanarata	Bulgaria	mineral deposit	felsic-intermediate igneous rock related	magmatic hydrothermal
Razdel	Bulgaria	occurrence	other	skarn and carbonate replacement, granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, pegmatite aplite
Babyak-Iztok	Bulgaria	occurrence	other	granitic igneous rocks and pegmatites, pegmatite aplite
Kremicovtsi	Bulgaria	mineral deposit	sediment-hosted	sedimentary
Izdremets	Bulgaria	mineral deposit	sediment-hosted	carbonate-hosted, sandstone-hosted

inspire_commodity	crm_2023	element	commodity_importance	mine_status	mining_activity_types	has_oreme	longitude	latitude	crm_2023_importance
Bauxite	aluminium or bauxite	Al					17.288438	43.668488	aluminium or bauxite - Not specified
Bauxite	aluminium or bauxite	Al					13.600719	45.165314	aluminium or bauxite - Not specified
Nickel (metal)	nickel	Ni	occurrence	no mine		no	24.049	66.405	nickel - Not specified
Cobalt (metal)	cobalt	Co	occurrence	no mine		no	24.87	66.439	cobalt - Not specified
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine		no	25.307	66.275	copper - Not specified
Platinum (metal)	PGM	PGM	occurrence	no mine		no	26.276	66.455	PGM - Not specified
Cobalt (metal)	cobalt	Co	small deposit	no mine		yes	25.279	66.111	cobalt - Not specified
Baryte or Barite (BaSO4)	baryte	Ba	large deposit	closed	underground	yes	16.20183	50.75885	baryte - large deposit
Black coal	coking coal	coking coal	very large deposit	operating	underground	yes	18.75889	50.19708	coking coal - large deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	medium sized deposit	notOperating	underground	yes	15.98699	51.68104	copper - medium sized deposit
Feldspar, nepheline	feldspar	feldspar	medium sized deposit	notOperating	surface mining	yes	15.77829	50.92327	feldspar - medium sized deposit
Phosphate rock	phosphate rock	phosphate rock	occurrence	notOperating	surface mining	yes	22.72056	51.54006	phosphate rock - occurrence
Manganese (metal)	manganese	Mn	small deposit		open pit	no	-6.92063	37.58406	manganese - small deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence		shaft	no	-6.61974	37.50268	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	large deposit		open pit and underground	no	-7.09749	37.57623	copper - large deposit
Cobalt (metal)	cobalt	Co	very large deposit		open pit	yes	-6.58487	37.70653	cobalt - very large deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	28.92602	-15.2247	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	28.31239	-15.6286	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	28.92602	-15.2247	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	27.3832	-15.0347	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	29.17492	-13.9254	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	32.32195	-12.9282	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	25.03314	-14.7847	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	28.01905	-15.4444	copper - occurrence
Bismuth (metal)	bismuth	Bi	occurrence	no mine	surface mining	no	29.38326	-15.5013	bismuth - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	large deposit	operating	underground	yes	24.07423	42.69959	copper - large deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	small deposit	notOperating	borehole mining	no	24.12727	42.53535	copper - small deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	notOperating	borehole mining	no	24.24492	42.42375	copper - occurrence
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	small deposit	closed	open pit and underground	yes	24.21303	42.35921	copper - small deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	small deposit	closed	underground	yes	27.5859	42.41539	copper - small deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	small deposit	closed	underground	yes	27.41043	42.34951	copper - small deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	occurrence	notOperating	borehole mining	no	26.65414	42.06111	copper - occurrence
Tungsten (metal)	tungsten	W	occurrence	notOperating	surface mining	no	23.67785	41.9597	tungsten - occurrence
Baryte or Barite (BaSO4)	baryte	Ba	small deposit	closed	open pit	yes	23.48715	42.78311	baryte - small deposit
Copper (metal)	copper	Cu	small deposit	closed	underground	yes	23.43711	43.01918	copper - small deposit

